

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF IMAGE ENHANCEMENT METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING POTATO LEAF DISEASES

Zhang Hongzhi,

*National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek,
Faculty of Applied Mathematics and intellectual Technologies
JiNing Normal University, School of Mathematics and statistic,
Ulanqab, Inner Mongolia, P. R. China*

Jining Normal University Scientific Research Project: Convolutional Neural Network-based Potato Leaf Disease Identification Method (jsky2024001)

Varlamova L.

*National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek,
Faculty of Applied Mathematics and intellectual Technologies*

ABSTRACT

Image enhancement is an important field in digital image processing, aimed at improving the visual quality of images or making them more suitable for specific application requirements. It employs a series of technical methods to highlight useful information in images, suppress or remove unwanted information, thereby enhancing the usability of images. This paper takes potato leaf disease images as the research object, theoretically analyses various traditional image enhancement methods, and uses MATLAB to simulate and implement multiple image enhancement effects on potato leaf disease images.

Keywords: image enhancement; transformation; histogram equalisation; adaptive contrast enhancement.

1 Background and Significance of the Study

Potato leaf disease identification is an important topic in the field of agriculture. Currently, most research on disease identification is based on neural networks, and successful neural networks contain a large number of parameters. Using supervised neural network models for leaf disease identification requires sufficient samples for training. However, in real life, due to factors such as the high cost of labelled samples or low disease incidence rates, it is often difficult to obtain sufficient training data, which is a common challenge in current plant disease identification research. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a data augmentation method capable of generating disease images to address the issue of insufficient training samples, thereby meeting the basic data requirements for deep learning training. This is of great significance for improving the accuracy of disease identification.

2 Image enhancement methods and experiments

Image enhancement is a method of modifying data without distorting its original intent. The number of samples can be increased using data enhancement techniques[1]. We can apply geometric transformations to generate enhancement parameters such as translation, scaling, rotation, mirroring, affine, etc[2], and we can also change the visual effect of the image by altering the brightness, saturation and sharpening of the image[3]. Specific data enhancement methods performed on sample images are as follows:

2.1 Translation

Translation is the process of moving a sample image horizontally or vertically by a certain length, thereby reducing the pixel variation in the image so that the image does not affect subsequent studies, usually by using a three-dimensional matrix consisting of three vectors. For example, given a value a , the width and length of the image will be shifted by a random value selected from the interval $[0, a]$. The result after image translation is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Result after image translation

2.2 Scaling

Scaling is the process of scaling a sample image size to a certain range. For example, given a value b , each image will be resized in the interval $[1 - b, 1 + b]$. The result of image scaling is shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Result after image scaling

2.3 Rotation

Rotation consists of turning an image by a random angle. For example, given a value θ , each figure will be rotated by an angle within the interval $[0, \theta]$. The result after rotating the image is shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Result after image rotation

2.4 Mirroring

Mirroring is to flip the sample image horizontally or vertically. The result of image mirroring are shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Result after image mirroring

2.5 Affine

Affine is a linear operation on each pixel of a sample image with a translation component that transforms the image pixels into another geometric space. The result of the affine transformation of the image are shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5: Result after affine transformation of the image

2.6 Sharpening

Sharpening of an image is the blurring of edges by focusing, which is an operation of focusing between pixels of an image to make the processed area of the image clearer and more colourful. The result of image sharpening using the Laplace operator are shown in Figure 6:

Figure 6: Result after image sharpening using the Laplace operator

2.7 Adjusting image saturation and brightness

Adjusting the saturation and brightness of an image is done by first obtaining the RGB pixel values for the entire image and then finding the pixel average of the image, each image pixel value is then multiplied or subtracted by the mean pixel of the image and multiplied by a contrast factor. Finally, each image pixel is multiplied by the mean pixel and a brightness factor is added to reassign each image value. The result after adjusting the saturation and brightness of the potato disease leaf images are shown in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Result after adjusting image saturation and brightness

2.8 Histogram equalisation

The histogram equalisation process resulted in an even and balanced distribution of brightness in the image, allowing the characteristic information of potato leaf spots to be displayed more clearly. The histogram is denoted by $H(P)$, and the usual range of grey levels is $[p_0, p_n]$. From the calculation, we can obtain that the output histogram $G(q)$ is balanced over the entire range of output grey levels.

$$\sum_{i=0}^n G(q_i) = \sum_{i=0}^n H(p_i) \quad (1)$$

The summed probability density sum statistic in the above equation is:

$$f = \frac{MN}{q_n - q_0} \quad (2)$$

integration leads to

$$MN \int_{q_0}^q \frac{1}{q_n - q_0} ds = \frac{MN(q_n - q_0)}{q_n - q_0} \int_{p_0}^p H(s) ds \quad (3)$$

it can be obtained that the luminance transformation T

$$q = T(p) = \frac{q_n - q_0}{MN} \int_{p_0}^p H(s) ds + q_0 \quad (4)$$

The result of the integration in Eq. (4) is the cumulative histogram, and the approximation to the continuous pixel luminance transform in (4) in the discrete case is

$$q = T(p) = \frac{q_n - q_0}{MN} \sum_{i=0}^n H(s) \Delta s + q_0 \quad (5)$$

The result obtained by histogram equalisation of potato disease leaf images are shown in Figure 8:

Figure 8: Result after histogram equalisation processing

The comparison result obtained by applying two-dimensional histogram equalisation and traditional histogram equalisation to potato disease leaf images are shown in Figure 9:

Figure 9

Comparison of result after two-dimensional histogram equalisation and traditional histogram equalisation

2.9 Adaptive Contrast Enhancement

Since the segmented leaf image is an RGB colour image, if the R, G and B channel component images are purely enhanced and the enhanced three-channel component images are directly merged, it will cause a change in the hue of the image, and the colour of the image will be changed. Therefore, in order to solve the change of image hue after enhancement, the leaf image is firstly converted from RGB colour space to HIS colour space, while the H and S channels represent the hue and saturation respectively, which do not need to be enhanced, so only the I (brightness) channel component image needs to be enhanced for contrast. Let $I(i, j)$ be the pixel value of the centre point of a window of size $(2n + 1) \times (2n + 1)$ pixels, then the average value $m(i, j)$ of the pixels in the $2n + 1$ -neighbourhood of the point (i, j) is

$$m(i, j) = \frac{1}{(2n + 1)^2} \sum_{k=i-n}^{i+n} \sum_{l=j-n}^{j+n} I(k, l) \quad (6)$$

The standard deviation σ is

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(2n + 1)^2} \sum_{k=i-n}^{i+n} \sum_{l=j-n}^{j+n} [I(k, l) - m(i, j)]^2} \quad (7)$$

Where n is a non-negative integer, k and l are represented as coordinates in a window of size $(2n + 1) \times (2n + 1)$ pixels. Let μ be the global pixel average of the component I image, β is the value of the parameter in the interval $[0, 1]$, then the pixel value $G(i, j)$ after enhancement of $I(i, j)$ can be expressed as

$$G(i, j) = \frac{\beta\mu}{\sigma} [I(i, j) - m(i, j)] + m(i, j) \quad (8)$$

The enhanced I-channel component image is merged with the H- and S-channel component images,

and then the colour space of the merged image is converted from the HIS colour space to the RGB colour space to complete the contrast enhancement of the leaf image. Let the contrast-enhanced image be Q. Since image Q is a three-channel image of R, G and B, the complementary pixel value $C(i, j)$ of any of its channels can be expressed as

$$C(i, j) = 255 - Q(i, j) \quad (9)$$

The image Q undergoes the equation (9) to find out the complementary images of its R, G, and B channel component images respectively, and the complementary images of each component are merged to obtain the complementary image of the image Q finally. The result obtained by applying adaptive contrast enhancement to images of potato disease leaves are shown in Figure 10:

Figure 10: Result after adaptive contrast enhancement processing

3 Conclusion

Traditional image enhancement is a fundamental technology in the field of computer vision. Its core objective is to optimise the visual presentation of images through a series of algorithms, thereby reinforcing the effective information contained within them and laying a reliable foundation for subsequent analysis, recognition, or experimental operations. The technical approach focuses on processing the statistical characteristics of image pixels, spatial domain features, or frequency domain features. Because it does not rely on large-scale data training, it has the significant advantages of being easy to understand, computationally efficient, and requiring low hardware resources. With the rapid development of deep learning technology, traditional image enhancement methods have not been eliminated. Instead, they often serve as the foundation or an important supplement to modern algorithm systems. Many deep learning models still rely on traditional methods for pre-processing, and the underlying principles of traditional methods also provide key inspiration for the architectural design of deep learning models.

In summary, traditional image enhancement can be considered a foundational technology in the field of computer vision. Although some of its functions have been replaced by modern methods in complex scenarios, it still has irreplaceable practical value in simple task processing, scenarios with high real-time requirements, and environments with limited hardware resources.

References

1. Wang Xing-Yue, Research on unbalanced data classification method of generative data enhancement [D]. Beijing jiaotong university, 2021. DOI: 10.26944/d.cnki.Gbfju.2021.000372.
2. ZHU Xiaohui, QIAN Liping, FU Wei. A review of research on image data enhancement techniques[J]. Software Guide, 2021, 20(05): 230-236.
3. ZHU Xiaohui, Qian Liping, Fu Wei, Research Review on image data enhancement techniques [J]. Journal of Software Guide, 2021, 20(05): 230-236.